

1 **Temporary reductions of stem CO₂ efflux during rainfall events across tree species**

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8

9 **Abstract**

10 Stem respiration is an important component of forest carbon cycling, yet its accurate quantification
11 remains challenging. While stem respiration is commonly measured as CO₂ efflux from the stem
12 surface (E_A), several processes can decouple measured fluxes from actual respiratory activity. In
13 this study, we investigated the influence of rainfall events on E_A across temperate tree species and
14 assessed the potential consequences for seasonal carbon budget estimates. Continuous automated
15 chamber measurements revealed distinct short-term decreases in E_A coinciding with rain events.
16 Time-lapse camera records confirmed that stem surfaces were frequently covered by a water film
17 during rainfall, suggesting that wet bark temporarily restricted CO₂ diffusion to the atmosphere.
18 Rain-related decreases in E_A accounted for up to 21% of the available seasonal data (May–October)
19 and caused up to 12% underestimation of seasonal sums of measured E_A . The largest impact was
20 observed in beech, followed by hornbeam and spruce, whereas oak and ash showed the smallest
21 underestimation. Our results demonstrate that rainfall can systematically bias E_A measurements
22 and lead to underestimation of seasonal and annual carbon fluxes from tree stems. Recognizing
23 and accounting for these temporary but repeated events is therefore essential for improving the
24 accuracy of forest carbon budget assessments under both current and future precipitation regimes.

26 **Keywords**

27 Bark wetting, carbon flux, diffusion resistance, forest, rainfall, stem respiration

30 **1 Introduction**

31 Forest respiration is a key component of the global carbon cycle, as it represents a major flux of
32 carbon dioxide (CO₂) from ecosystems to the atmosphere. Although stem respiration generally
33 accounts for only about 5–25% of total forest ecosystem respiration (Acosta et al., 2008; Khomik
34 et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Calcerrada et al., 2014; Song et al., 2023; Yang et al.,
35 2016; Zha et al., 2007), it plays a non-negligible role.

36 Stem respiration is most commonly measured as CO₂ efflux (E_A) from the stem surface using
37 chamber systems. This method provides valuable insights into both short-term dynamics and long-
38 term seasonal trends. However, E_A does not necessarily equal the actual respiration of stem tissues
39 at the measurement point. Several processes can alter the relationship, including transport of

40 dissolved CO₂ by the xylem sap (Teskey et al. 2008; Tarvainen et al. 2018), partial CO₂ refixation
41 by photosynthetically active cells in the bark (Dukat et al., 2024), and diffusional limitations within
42 woody tissues (Steppe et al., 2007). Nevertheless, E_A remains the most widely applied and
43 technically feasible indicator of stem respiration.

44 Temporal E_A dynamics is primarily driven by temperature (Darenova et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2021).
45 During the period of new wood formation, E_A is enhanced due to extra energy demands (Darenova
46 et al., 2020; Rodríguez-calcerrada et al., 2019). From our experience and previous studies, the
47 diurnal courses of E_A follows the temperature fluctuations. We, however, observed unexpected
48 temporal decreases in our E_A datasets from automated continuous measurement systems. These
49 data were not flagged by the data quality indicator, therefore, they were not assessed as error
50 measurements. We did not find any reason stem respiration to drop suddenly. The decreases,
51 however, coincided with rain events. Time-laps camera observations confirmed that the stem
52 surface was covered by a water film (Fig. S1). We assumed that such surface wetting temporarily
53 restricted E_A by limiting CO₂ diffusion to the atmosphere. This phenomenon has so far received
54 little attention. Steppe et al. (2007) and Salomón et al. (2016) investigated the role of woody tissue
55 and bark water status in controlling CO₂ diffusion resistance. They found that resistance to radial
56 CO₂ diffusion was higher at night, when woody tissue and bark water reservoirs were refilled in
57 the absence of transpiration, than during the day, when transpiration lowered water content. This
58 pattern reflects the much slower diffusion of CO₂ in water compared with air (Nobel, 2009).

59 Rain-related reductions in measured E_A may systematically bias seasonal and annual forest carbon
60 budget estimates. Such discrepancies are likely influenced by interannual and site-specific variation
61 in precipitation regimes and may also differ among tree species. Therefore, the main objective of
62 this study was to quantify the effect of rainfall events on stem CO₂ efflux measurements in different
63 tree species. Specifically, we aimed i) to identify and quantify short-term decreases in E_A during
64 and immediately after rain events, ii) to estimate the contribution of these decreases to total
65 seasonal stem CO₂ efflux, and iii) to compare the magnitude of the effect among tree species with
66 contrasting bark characteristics and crown architecture. The study included Norway spruce as a
67 representative conifer, along with broadleaved species—beech and hornbeam with smooth bark,
68 and oak and ash with rough bark. Our findings provide new insights into the processes that alter
69 measurements of stem respiration and support more accurate estimates of forest carbon fluxes.

70

71 2 Materials and Methods

72

73 2.1 Sites

74 Measurements were carried out at three sites: a beech forest (European beech, *Fagus sylvatica* L.),
75 a spruce forest (Norway spruce, *Picea abies* L.), and a broadleaved mixed forest dominated by
76 common hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.), English oak (*Quercus robur* L.), and narrow-leaved ash
77 (*Fraxinus angustifolia* Vahl). Site and stand characteristics are summarised in Table S1.

78

79 2.2 CO₂ efflux measurements

80 We analysed data from six chambers installed on beech and spruce trees, and four chambers on
81 hornbeam, oak, and ash trees. The chambers were a part of the 12-chamber automated measurement
82 systems. The control unit consisted of an infrared gas analyser (Li-840, LI-COR, Lincoln, NE,
83 USA), and a personal computer equipped with control software, as well as additional analogue
84 input and digital output hardware. The chamber closing was enabled by pressure air supplied by a
85 compressor and regulated through a system of valves, and pneumatic pistons fixed on the chambers.
86 Each chamber (Fig. S2) comprised a frame and a chamber head. The frames were rectangular with
87 inner dimensions 7x12 cm on spruce and 9x15 cm on the other tree species, and they had a neoprene
88 seals against the tree trunk. A groove a few millimetres wide, filled with rubber, secured the seal
89 between the frame and chamber head. The chamber heads were made of stainless steel and had a
90 half-cylinder shape. Chambers were attached to the tree trunk at breast height on the northern side
91 using two belts.

92 For beech, hornbeam, and spruce (all with relatively smooth bark), the neoprene seal was sufficient.
93 In contrast, oak and ash had thick, rough outer bark that needed careful removal with a chisel to
94 avoid damaging living tissues. Bark was removed only along the frame circumference where the
95 neoprene seal was applied; the area inside the frame remained untouched.

96 Stem CO₂ efflux (E_A) was measured sequentially in all chambers, with data collected every 2 h at
97 each position. After chamber closure, air was circulated between the chamber and the analyzer,
98 followed by a 60-second equilibration period. The system then recorded 20 CO₂ concentration
99 values at 10-second intervals for efflux calculation, using the following equation:

100
$$E_A = \frac{P \cdot V \cdot (c_2 - c_1)}{R \cdot T \cdot S \cdot t},$$

101 where P is air pressure (Pa), V is the volume of the system (m^3), c_1 and c_2 are consecutive CO_2
102 concentrations (mol mol^{-1}), R is the molar gas constant, T is sample air temperature (K), S is the
103 stem surface area enclosed by the frame (m^2) and t is measurement interval (10 s).

104 For each 200 s measurement, mean E_A and standard deviation (SD) were calculated. SD served as
105 an indicator of data quality; if SD exceeded the efflux value, the data were excluded. Across 2020–
106 2024, 64–96% of seasonal data were available for analyses (Table 1)

107

108 2.3 *Meteorological measurements*

109 Stem temperature sensors (PT 100, Sensit, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Czech Republic) were
110 integrated into the stem CO_2 efflux systems and measured temperature at the stem surface beneath
111 the chambers. Precipitation was continuously monitored with a rain gauge (MetOne 386, Met One
112 Instruments, Inc., Grants Pass, OR, USA) installed on towers above the forest stands.

113

114 2.4 *Data processing*

115 The effect of rain on stem CO_2 efflux was determined using the following approach (see also the
116 schematic in Fig. S3):

117 1. Detection of rain-related decreases in E_A

118 We identified periods when measured stem E_A showed unexpected declines that coincided
119 with rainfall events. These declines were recognized by discrepancies between the observed
120 E_A and the values expected from the temperature–efflux relationship.

121 2. Modelling the expected E_A

122 To obtain the reference efflux (E_m), we fitted an exponential temperature–efflux model
123 using a 10-day moving window. For model fitting, we excluded data affected by the rain-
124 related decreases. This provided a smooth, temperature-driven prediction of E_A under
125 unaffected conditions.

126 3. Quantifying the effect of decreases

127 For each rain-related decrease, we calculated the ratio of the measured E_A to the modelled
128 E_m at the same time. This ratio represents the relative reduction of E_A due to the presence
129 of surface water films during rain events.

130 4. Seasonal impact assessment

131 We replaced the periods of rain-related decreases with the corresponding modelled values
132 (E_m).

133 Using these corrected time series, we calculated seasonal sums of CO₂ efflux both with and
134 without the rain-related E_A decreases. The contribution of the decreases to seasonal totals
135 was determined by comparing these sums. Calculations of sums were based only on
136 available data, without gap-filling for missing values

137
138 To determine the E_A -temperature relationship, Q_{10} was calculated as:

139 $Q_{10} = e^{10 \cdot \alpha}$,

140 where α is a function growth parameter derived from the exponential relationship between E_A and
141 stem temperature.

142 A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was used to test differences between tree species in the
143 proportional impact of rain-related E_A decreases on seasonal E_A sums. Statistical analyses were
144 performed using SigmaPlot version 15.0 (Systat Software Inc., San Jose, CA, USA).

145

146

147

148 **3 Results**

149

150 *3.1 Micrometeorology*

151 Precipitation during the experimental seasons (May – October) was generally highest in spruce
152 forest and lowest in the broad-leaved mixed forest. Seasonal totals ranged from 345 to 624 mm in
153 the beech forest, from 602 to 1066 mm in the spruce forest, and from 304 to 517 mm in the broad-
154 leave mixed forest. A summary of precipitation and the number of rainy days for each season is
155 provided in Table 1.

156

157 *3.2 Rain-related decreases in E_A*

158 Rain-related decreases in E_A accounted for up to 21% of the available seasonal data (May–October)
159 (Table 1). The largest proportion was observed in beech ($13 \pm 5\%$), followed by hornbeam ($9 \pm$
160 2%), spruce ($8 \pm 3\%$), ash ($3 \pm 1\%$), and oak ($2 \pm 2\%$). The biggest decreases occurred in beech,
161 where most reductions were concentrated between 40–60% (Fig. 1). In hornbeam, decreases

162 peaked at 20–30%, while in spruce they were more evenly distributed, ranging from 10 to 60%.
163 The smallest reductions were observed in oak and ash, generally between 10 and 30%.
164 The rain-related decreases in E_A caused up to 12% underestimation of seasonal sums of measured
165 E_A (Fig. 2). The biggest impact was observed in beech with mean underestimation of $5.3 \pm 2.8\%$,
166 followed by hornbeam ($3.3 \pm 1.6\%$) and spruce ($2.2 \pm 2.4\%$). The smallest underestimation was in
167 oak ($0.3 \pm 0.5\%$) and ash ($1.1 \pm 1.4\%$).

168

169 3.3 *After-rainfall period*

170 To test whether the temporary inhibition of CO_2 release from stems during rain events leads to an
171 increase in E_A after the rainfall ends and the bark dries, we analyzed the difference between
172 measured and modeled E_A in six hours following rain (more precisely three measurements after
173 measured E_A returned modeled values). Within six hours after rainfall (corresponding to three E_A
174 measurements), E_A tended to increase in beech, spruce, and hornbeam, most frequently by 0–10%
175 (Fig. 1). In contrast, no clear post-rain increases were observed in oak or ash.

176

177 3.4 *Effect of rain-related E_A decreases on Q_{10}*

178 To illustrate the impact of rain-related E_A decreases on E_A interpretation, we selected one chamber
179 on beech (the species with the strongest rainfall effect on E_A) in 2024. We compared Q_{10} values
180 calculated from the whole measured dataset and from a dataset in which the rain-related decreases
181 were removed. Using a 10-day moving window, Q_{10} in the corrected dataset fluctuated consistently
182 between 1.5 and 2.0 throughout the season (Fig. 3-A). In contrast, when based on all measured
183 data, Q_{10} exhibited several large deviations, reaching values as high as 15.4. At a monthly time
184 step, the discrepancy between the two datasets was reduced but remained substantial (Fig. 3-B).

185

186 4 Discussion

187 In our study, we observed a temporal decrease in E_A that was so steep it could not be explained by
188 the typical temperature drop that often accompanies rainy weather. Moreover, there is no
189 physiological reason for such a pronounced decline in living cell respiration, which is the main
190 source of CO_2 production. On the contrary, (Salomón et al., 2016) observed an increase in stem
191 CO_2 concentrations after rain. The explanation must therefore be sought in factors affecting CO_2
192 efflux from the stem to the atmosphere.

193 A thin water film covering tree stems during and shortly after rain events, or bark saturated with
194 water, can represent a temporary barrier for CO₂ diffusion from the stem to the atmosphere. This
195 makes it more difficult to estimate the actual amount of CO₂ respired by living stem cells and
196 released to the atmosphere. The effect of bark water content on radial CO₂ diffusion resistance has
197 been confirmed by (Salomón et al., 2019). Generally, the rate of CO₂ diffusion is approximately
198 10⁴ times slower in water than in air (Nobel, 2009). This fundamental difference in diffusion rates
199 highlights why even a thin water film may substantially alter CO₂ efflux dynamics.

200 Overall, E_A was most affected by rain in beech, followed by hornbeam and spruce. The smallest
201 effect was observed in ash and oak. Tree species and stand structure strongly influence both the
202 amount of precipitation reaching the stem and the intensity of stemflow. In general, stemflow is
203 higher in broadleaves than in conifers due to canopy morphology (Barbier et al., 2009; Kantor and
204 Šach, 2009). This likely explains the smaller rain effect on E_A in spruce compared with beech and
205 hornbeam, despite higher seasonal precipitation at the spruce site. Differences among deciduous
206 species can be explained by bark roughness (Novosadová et al., 2023). The smooth bark of beech
207 and hornbeam has a smaller soaking area and faster water flow down the trunk, whereas the rough
208 bark of oak and ash increases soaking capacity and slows water runoff. These bark-related
209 differences in water retention may therefore control both the intensity and duration of rain-related
210 E_A reductions. A further methodological influence cannot be excluded: in oak and ash, a certain
211 layer of outer bark was removed to achieve a tight seal of the chamber, which may have introduced
212 an artificial barrier to stemflow around the frame.

213 In beech, spruce, and hornbeam, the strongest rain effects were observed in 2020, both in term of
214 the proportion of data classified as rain-related E_A decreases and the magnitude of seasonal E_A
215 underestimation (Table 1). Notably, 2020 experienced the highest seasonal precipitation sum,
216 accompanied by a larger number of rainy days compared with other years. This result highlights
217 the role of precipitation regime in affecting stem CO₂ fluxes.

218 The data from rain-related decrease periods are of good technical quality, but they do not represent
219 the true temporal pattern of CO₂ production in stems. This raises the question of whether such data
220 should be included in datasets used for estimating tree CO₂ budgets. We may expect that CO₂ not
221 released during wet periods could later be emitted in a different location or at a different time.
222 Higher stem CO₂ concentrations relative to the atmosphere due to radial diffusion barriers are well
223 known (Steppe et al., 2007), and temporary strengthening of these barriers during rain can further

224 be released, potentially causing a transient acceleration of E_A . Indeed, we observed increased E_A
225 within six hours after rain-suppressed E_A periods. This post-rain increases typically ranged from 0
226 to 20%, though it was not consistently observed. While the E_A drop during rain was rapid, recovery
227 to expected values was often more gradual, probably depending on the speed of surface drying.
228 Moreover, the stem surface inside the chamber frame did not dry uniformly, which complicated
229 the determination of the precise end of rain-related wet conditions. However, the post-rain
230 increases were generally smaller and shorter than the decreases and did not appear to compensate
231 for the presumed CO_2 accumulation within stems. Thus, the ultimate fate of the CO_2 respired during
232 rain events remains uncertain and may involve its dissolution in xylem sap and subsequent upward
233 transport. CO_2 can be then released to the atmosphere or re-assimilated by the photosynthetically
234 active cells later in upper stem parts, branches or leaves (Salomón et al., 2021; Teskey et al., 2008).
235 This would shift the spatial and temporal pattern of CO_2 efflux beyond what stem chambers detect.
236 Although the rain-related decreases accounted for only a few percent of seasonal E_A , including
237 them in datasets can strongly bias models based on the E_A –temperature relationship. During rain,
238 air temperature typically drops. If such periods are included, the combination of lower E_A and lower
239 temperature produces an artificially steep regression slope between E_A and temperature. This can
240 substantially overestimate the temperature sensitivity parameter Q_{10} . Using a 10-day moving
241 window for Q_{10} calculation, inclusion of rain-related decreases can yield values several times
242 higher than the true sensitivity (Fig. 3). Longer time windows reduced this overestimation but did
243 not eliminate it. However, longer periods are also influenced by additional factors, especially
244 differences in stem growth status (Darenova et al., 2018). Therefore, careful data filtering is
245 essential before applying E_A –temperature models to avoid introducing systematic errors into
246 estimates of forest carbon dynamics.

247

248 **5 Conclusions**

249 Reduced CO_2 efflux caused by wet bark generally led to only a slight underestimation – typically
250 a few percent – of seasonal CO_2 emissions, which can be considered negligible. However, our
251 results demonstrate that in regions with high precipitation and in beech forests, or in stands
252 dominated by tree species with fine bark, this underestimation can become substantial.
253 Furthermore, including rain-related stem CO_2 efflux data without correction can significantly bias
254 models that rely on the relationship between CO_2 efflux and temperature.

255 Accurately quantifying the dynamics of CO₂ efflux and internal CO₂ storage during rain events is
256 therefore essential for assessing tree carbon fluxes. Combining high-frequency efflux
257 measurements with internal CO₂ concentration monitoring could help determine whether CO₂
258 produced during rain events is later released to the atmosphere or redirected elsewhere within the
259 tree.

260

261 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process.**

262 Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies should only be used in the writing process to improve
263 the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited
264 the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

265

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274

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348

349 **Table 1**

350 Micrometeorological conditions and data availability reported for all years. The proportion of
 351 available stem CO₂ efflux (E_A) data was expressed relative to 100%, corresponding to values
 352 recorded every two hours throughout the season. The proportion of rain-related E_A decreases was
 353 calculated relative to the available seasonal dataset. Finally, the proportion of E_A decreases relative
 354 to seasonal E_A was derived from datasets in which rain-related decreases had been replaced by
 355 modeled values.

	Beech	Spruce	Hornbeam	Oak	Ash
Precipitation (mm; May – October)					
2020	624	1066		517	
2021	359	642		304	
2022	345	602		315	
2023	463	629		312	
2024	564	767		343	
Mean (SD)	471 (123)	741 (192)		358 (90)	
Number of rainy days (May – October)					
2020	91	101		101	
2021	61	79		94	
2022	77	98		103	
2023	66	88		90	
2024	71	85		94	
Mean (SD)	73 (12)	90 (9)		96 (5)	
Data availability (%)					
2020	86	93	86	87	86
2021	71	82	95	96	95
2022	81	81	64	64	64
2023	92	76	97	95	96
2024	89	94	82	86	87
Mean (SD)	84 (8)	85 (8)	85 (13)	86 (13)	86 (13)
Rain related E_A decreases (%)					
2020	21	11	13	0	2
2021	9	8	10	3	5
2022	12	4	7	3	3

2023	10	9	9	1	3
2024	13	6	6	0	3
Mean (SD)	13 (5)	8 (3)	9 (2)	2 (2)	3 (1)

Proportion of decreases to seasonal E_A

2020	9.7 (1.6)	3.2 (3.6)	5.5 (0.3)	0.1 (0.1)	1.2 (1.7)
2021	4.1 (3.3)	2.4 (2.1)	3.7 (1.0)	1.0 (0.6)	1.9 (2.1)
2022	4.7 (0.8)	1.3 (1.9)	2.6 (1.2)	0.4 (0.5)	1.0 (1.4)
2023	3.6 (1.4)	2.4 (2.8)	2.9 (1.1)	0.2 (0.3)	0.7 (1.0)
2024	4.3 (0.9)	1.8 (1.8)	1.8 (0.8)	0.0 (0.0)	0.7 (1.1)

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Fig. 1. Distributions of proportional changes in stem CO_2 efflux (E_A) induced by rainfall relative to the temperature- E_A model (upper panels), and proportional changes in E_A within six hours after rain. Counts were normalized by the number of chambers (six for beech and spruce; four for hornbeam, oak, and ash).

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 366 **Fig. 2.** Proportional impact of rain-related decreases in stem CO₂ efflux (EA) on seasonal EA
 367 sums. The figure shows the differences between measured data and the datasets in which the rain-
 368 related decreases were replaced with values from the EA-temperature relationship. Different
 369 letters indicate statistically significant differences among species (One-Way-ANOVA, p<0.05).
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371
 372 **Fig. 3.** Temperature sensitivity of stem CO₂ efflux (Q_{10}) calculated from two datasets: all measured
 373 data and data with the rain-related decreases removed. A – Q_{10} estimated using a 10-day moving
 374 window, B – Q_{10} estimated using a monthly time step.
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